

Chelating Tendencies of some N-(2-Methyl 4-Substituted-phenylazo)Phenylglycine Dyes

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The step formation constants of chelates of six N-(2-methyl 4-substitutedphenylazo)phenylglycine dyes with copper(II) and nickel(II) ions have been determined at 25°, and at an ionic strength of 0.1M (NaClO₄) in 50% aqueous dioxan (v/v) medium, employing pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti. Logarithms of the values of overall conditional formation constants of the dyes, viz. *o*-ClG, *m*-ClG, *p*-ClG, *p*-OCH₃G, 3-Cl, *p*-CH₃G and 5-Cl *o*-CH₃G for various complexation equilibria were found to be : protonation 5.54, 4.54, 5.24, 5.25, 5.36 and 5.17 ; copper chelates 7.27, 6.63, 7.18, 7.04, 7.55 and 6.87 ; and for nickel chelates 6.30, 6.23, 6.29, 6.23, 6.77 and 6.36 respectively. The effects of various substitutions on the dye molecule upon the stability of their metal chelates have been discussed on the basis of steric hindrance affecting the chelating tendency of the amino acid i.e. glycine of the dye molecule.

SCANTY work on the preparation and application of azo dyes of N-phenylglycine is reported in literature and only one patent report is available¹. Srivastava and Mehrotra² described the preparation and tinctorial properties of several N-(2-methyl-4-substitutedphenylazo)phenylglycine dyes for the first time. To understand the chemistry of possible application of this class of dyes as metalized dyes it is primarily desirable to investigate the

metal-dye interaction equilibria in solution. This has been accomplished in the present work by a study of stepwise equilibria in their complexation processes with Cu(II) and Ni(II) ions in solution. The study of the influence of various substitutions, on the chelating tendencies of closely related ligands, is of interest, and an extension of the synthetic work of the dyes was also undertaken by introducing few more substituents on the phenyl nuclei of the dyes³ (Table 1).

TABLE I.

No.	Compound	Colour	m.p.*	Yield %	Solubility of the dye
1.	2,OCH ₃ ,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Dirty yellow	146	60	Ethanol, Dioxan, Acetone, Mineral Acids and dilute NaOH
2.	4,OCH ₃ ,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Dirty yellow	133	55	—do—
3.	2,OH,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Light grey	154	58	—do—
4.	3,OH,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Violet	170	56	—do—
5.	2,COOH,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Reddish brown	178	64	Dilute NaOH, Acetic Acid
6.	3,COOH,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Brown	172	85	—do—
7.	4,COOH,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Yellowish orange	203	90	—do—
8.	4,SO ₃ H,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Violet	210	45	Pyridine, Nitrobenzene, Dilute NaOH
			Sints. at 236—244		
9.	3,CH ₃ ,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Yellowish orange	128	60	Ethanol, Dioxan, Acetone
10.	3,4,Cl,CH ₃ ,C ₆ H ₃ -R	Turmeric yellow	173	91	—do—
11.	5,2,Cl,CH ₃ ,C ₆ H ₃ -R	Reddish orange	160	92	—do—
12.	3,4,NO ₂ ,OCH ₃ ,C ₆ H ₃ -R	Reddish orange	163	90	—do—
13.	2,Cl,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Orange	154	90	—do—
14.	3,Cl,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Yellow	148	90	—do—
15.	4,Cl,C ₆ H ₄ -R	Turmeric yellow	153—154	92	—do—

* All the m.ps. are uncorrected.

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The effects of various substitutions on the dye molecule, upon the stability constants of the metal chelates have been studied and the values have been discussed on the basis of steric hindrance affecting the chelating tendency of the amino acid i.e. glycine of the dye molecule. The step formation constants of copper and nickel chelates of the following six compounds :

- (1) N-[2-methyl4-(2'-chlorophenylazo)]phenylglycine (abbr. *o*-ClG)
- (2) N-[2-methyl4-(3'-chlorophenylazo)]phenylglycine (abbr. *m*-ClG)
- (3) N-[2-methyl4-(4'-chlorophenylazo)]phenylglycine (abbr. *p*-ClG)
- (4) N-[2-methyl4-(4'-methoxyphenylazo)]phenylglycine (abbr. *p*-OCH₃G)
- (5) N-[2-methyl4-(3'-chloro 4'-methylphenylazo)]phenylglycine (abbr. 3-Cl *p*-CH₃G)
- (6) N-[2-methyl4-(5'-chloro 2'-methylphenylazo)]phenylglycine (abbr. 5-Cl *o*-CH₃G)

were determined at 25° and at an ionic strength of 0.1M (NaClO₄) in 50% aqueous dioxan (v/v) medium, employing pH-metric titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁴ with the help of various computational methods described by them⁵. The studies have also furnished information on the proton-ligand stability constants of the dyes.

Experimental

Solutions and related materials :

All the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled CO₂-free water.

Cupric perchlorate solution was obtained by dissolving cupric oxide (E. Merck) in a known excess of perchloric acid. Nickel perchlorate solution was obtained by treating an excess of basic nickel carbonate [prepared by adding sodium bicarbonate (B.D.H., AnalaR) solution to an aqueous nickel nitrate (B.D.H., AnalaR) solution] with perchloric acid and then adding a known excess of perchloric acid to the filtrate. The metal contents in the solution were estimated by EDTA titrations. A suitable volume of both the solutions was separately diluted to get an acidic solution of 0.005M metal perchlorate in 50% aqueous dioxan medium.

Perchloric acid (E. Merck) solution in 50% aqueous dioxan was prepared and standardized against standard alkali.

A CO₂-free sodium hydroxide (B.D.H., AnalaR) solution in 50% aqueous dioxan was prepared and standardized against standard oxalic acid (B.D.H., AnalaR).

A concentrated solution of sodium perchlorate (B.D.H., AnalaR) was prepared in water, standardized and then suitably diluted to get a stock solution (0.5M) in 50% aqueous dioxan.

Stock solutions of the chelating ligands were prepared by dissolving accurately weighed amounts first in pure dioxan and then suitably diluting them with water with constant shaking to obtain 0.005M solution in 50% aqueous dioxan.

Procedure :

For pH-titrations, mixtures containing (A) acid (perchloric acid+sodium perchlorate), (B) ligand (mixture A+dye solution), (C) chelate (mixture B+metal solution), were taken. Since the metal solutions already contained a known amount of perchloric acid, a further equivalent amount of the same was added to mixtures A and B as well. The total volume of the titration mixture was then raised to 50 ml by adding 50% aqueous dioxan. Mixtures A, B and C were separately titrated against standard alkali in 50% aqueous dioxan pH-metrically till a pH of about 11.5 was reached in each case. The final concentrations in all the systems were generally of the order : N°=ca. 0.55M ; E°=ca. 0.0125M ; TC_{Lo} = 0.0025 ; TC_{Mo}=0.0005 and μ = 0.1M. The symbols have the usual meaning as described in ref. 4-5.

From the titration curves, the average number of protons associated with the ligand (\bar{n}_A), average number of ligands attached per metal ion (\bar{n}), and free ligand exponent (pL) were calculated using the formulae of Irving and Rossotti⁴, and from these parameters the formation curves were plotted corresponding to proton-ligand and metal-ligand systems, and the formation constants were determined by usual computational methods⁵.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand system : Basolo and Chen⁶ determined the dissociation constants of several N-alkylglycines and N-dialkylglycines which exist as zwitterion in solution. The dyes studied in the present investigation are N-substituted glycines and are also expected to behave as zwitterion in solution.

N-(2-methyl 4-substitutedphenylazo)phenylglycine dyes (being written here as HSG to facilitate onward discussions) may be represented structurally, in general, as :

where X, Y = H, Cl, CH₃ and OCH₃.

They would possess the following zwitterion structure

and exist as

in the initial stages of titration by accepting one proton from the strongly acidic medium. The dissociation of this species may be expected to occur in the following steps

It was noted (figs. omitted) that the ligand curve (B') was shifted slightly to the left of the acid titration curve (A') at lower pH values. This indicated gradual neutralization of -CO₂H group of the zwitterionic species, H₂⁺SG, which was complete at a pH where the curve B' crossed the curve A'. The onward course followed by the curve B' to the right of A' indicated the neutralization of cationic acid i.e. N⁺H₂ group of the zwitterion.

The difference of volume between the ligand and the acid titration curve (v'—v'') at lower pH values corresponding to the neutralization of -COOH group was so small that it was not possible to calculate reliable \bar{n}_A values in that range for all the dyes. However, the values of (v'—v'') after the curve B'

had crossed the curve A', were sufficiently reliable, from which \bar{n}_A values were calculated and formation curves of proton-ligand system for all the dyes obtained, and the values of the protonation constants obtained are recorded in Table 2.

In the initial stages of titration, the colour of the titrating mixture was orange red in case of all the dyes, which gradually changed to yellow with the increase in pH. It was, however, not possible to detect the exact pH at which the change in colour occurred, still the colour changes to the best approximation from orange red to yellow were observed in all the ligands in the pH range 3.5 to 4.1. This suggests that the transition of orange red species H₂⁺SG to yellow HSG takes place in solution. The subsequent transition from HSG to SG⁻ is not accompanied by any distinct change in colour.

It has also been noted that the colour change from orange red to yellow occurs almost at a pH where the ligand titration curve B' departs from the acid titration curve A', which to an approximation supports the fact that at this pH the neutralization of -COOH group of the zwitterionic species H₂⁺SG is almost complete and neutralization of yellow HSG species commences.

This may be clearly understood that the term pH (B) corresponds to the pH meter readings in 50% aqueous dioxan medium and the only significance of the practical proton-ligand stability constants obtained in this manner is their being convenient intermediates in the determination of the stability constants of metal-complexes⁷.

Metal-ligand system :

Though opacity/precipitation appeared in chelate titration in all the systems (in copper-dye systems generally at pH ~ 6 and in nickel-dye systems either at pH < 6.9 or pH > 8), yet none were observed at pH corresponding to the hydrolysis of respective metal ions (pH of hydrolysis in aqueous medium⁸ ; for Cu²⁺ = 4.8 ; for Ni²⁺ = 7.6. These data can be used for comparison, as behaviour of 50% aqueous dioxan medium as far as hydrolysis of metal ions is concerned, is almost similar as in aqueous medium⁹). This observation in conformity with the fact that pH at points of departure of chelate titration curve from the ligand titration curve also did not correspond to the pH of hydrolysis of respective metal ions, suggests in consequence that the displacement of chelate titration curve from ligand titration curve was not

due to the hydrolysis of metal ion. Since the solutions employed are very dilute, possibility of existence of hydrogen, hydroxyl bearing and polynuclear complexes could reasonably be ignored.

The stability constants of metal chelates were determined from formation curves of metal-dye systems, applying various computational methods⁵, whichever were applicable and the average values of stability constants obtained are recorded in Table 2.

It was noted that copper(II) and nickel(II) both form chelates in two steps with various N-(2-methyl 4-substituted-phenylazo)phenylglycines. The values of step constants in all the systems show that there is not much difference in the magnitude of the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$, which indicates that the formation of the two species is not independent. From the stability constant data it is also apparent that copper-dye chelates are more stable than the corresponding nickel-dye chelates.

TABLE 2—PROTONATION AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF N-(2-METHYL 4-SUBSTITUTEDPHENYLAZO) PHENYLGLYCINES IN 50% AQUEOUS DIOXAN MEDIUM AT 0.1M IONIC STRENGTH (25°)

Chelate	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_n$
H ⁺ — <i>o</i> -ClG	5.54	—	5.54
H ⁺ — <i>m</i> -ClG	4.54	—	4.54
H ⁺ — <i>p</i> -ClG	5.24	—	5.24
H ⁺ — <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ G	5.25	—	5.25
H ⁺ —3-Cl <i>p</i> -CH ₃ G	5.36	—	5.36
H ⁺ —5-Cl <i>o</i> -CH ₃ G	5.17	—	5.17
Cu(II)— <i>o</i> -ClG	4.01	3.26	7.27
Cu(II)— <i>m</i> -ClG	3.46	3.17	6.63
Cu(II)— <i>p</i> -ClG	3.93	3.25	7.18
Cu(II)— <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ G	3.91	3.13	7.04
Cu(II)—3-Cl <i>p</i> -CH ₃ G	4.10	3.45	7.55
Cu(II)—5-Cl <i>o</i> -CH ₃ G	3.58	3.29	6.87
Ni(II)— <i>o</i> -ClG	3.43	2.87	6.30
Ni(II)— <i>m</i> -ClG	3.33	2.90	6.23
Ni(II)— <i>p</i> -ClG	3.29	3.00	6.29
Ni(II)— <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ G	3.35	2.88	6.23
Ni(II)—3-Cl <i>p</i> -CH ₃ G	3.58	3.19	6.77
Ni(II)—5-Cl <i>o</i> -CH ₃ G	3.42	2.94	6.36

In order to investigate the steric hindrance (if any) caused to the amino acid i.e. glycine of the dye molecule, ratios of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ of glycine chelates of Cu(II) [Cu(II)-G] and nickel(II) [Ni(II)-G] to those of each of metal-dye chelates were

calculated, which is shown in the last two columns of the table 3 as $\log (K_{1G}/K_{1HSG})$ and $\log (K_{2G}/K_{2HSG})$ where K_{1G} , K_{2G} and K_{1HSG} , K_{2HSG} stand for the step formation constants of metal chelates of glycine and the dye respectively. As can be seen from the table 3, the decrease in the values of stability constants of dye chelates as compared to glycine chelates, shows clearly that the chelating tendencies of these substitutedglycines is less than that of glycine. N-(2-methyl 4-substitutedphenylazo)phenylglycine which is a N-substitutedglycine may be represented as

and X, Y=H, Cl, CH₃ and OCH₃ for convenience of discussion. It is evident from the table that the ratios $\log (K_{1G}/K_{1HSG})$ and $\log (K_{2G}/K_{2HSG})$ both for copper and nickel for various substituents X, Y on the dye molecule are almost of the same order, suggesting that the steric hindrance on the amino acid i.e. glycine of the dye molecule is largely due to -R and effect of X, Y substituents is negligible.

The values of $\log (K_{1G}/K_{1HSG})$ are a measure of the effect that the substitution has upon the chelating tendencies of their amino acids and the values observed for $\log (K_{2G}/K_{2HSG})$ furnish some indication as to the effect of increasing steric hindrance upon the entrance of the second dye molecule in the coordination sphere as compared to glycine itself (vide 6). Basolo and Chen⁶ have, however, shown that in the case of various N-alkylglycines and N-dialkylglycines, presence of one molecule of substituted glycine in the complex offers no greater resistance to the entry of the second molecule than water did to the entry of the first substituted glycine molecule. In the present investigation also the data $\log (K_{2G}/K_{2HSG})$ indicate that no greater hindrance is caused to the entry of the second dye molecule than that caused to the entry of the first dye molecule by solvent molecules.

It may be mentioned that owing to weak complexing properties of the azo group in the absence of any suitable donor group located in an ortho position to the azo group, its participation in coordination appears less likely.

TABLE 3.—COMPARISON OF STABILITY CONSTANT DATA OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II) CHELATES OF GLYCINE WITH THOSE OF N-(2-METHYL 4-SUBSTITUTEDPHENYLAZO) PHENYLGLYCINES

Chelate	log K_1	log K_2	log (K_{1G}/K_{1HSG})	Log (K_{2G}/K_{2HSG})
Cu(II)—G*	8.38	6.87	—	—
Cu(II)— <i>o</i> -ClG	4.01	3.26	4.37	3.61
Cu(II)— <i>m</i> -ClG	3.46	3.17	4.92	3.70
Cu(II)— <i>p</i> -ClG	3.93	3.25	4.45	3.62
Cu(II)— <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ G	3.91	3.15	4.47	3.74
Cu(II)—3-Cl <i>p</i> -CH ₃ G	4.10	3.45	4.28	3.42
Cu(II)—5-Cl <i>o</i> -CH ₃ G	3.58	3.29	4.80	3.58
Ni(II)—G*	5.86	4.78	—	—
Ni(II)— <i>o</i> -ClG	3.43	2.87	2.43	1.91
Ni(II)— <i>m</i> -ClG	3.33	2.90	2.53	1.88
Ni(II)— <i>p</i> -ClG	3.29	3.00	2.57	1.78
Ni(II)— <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ G	3.35	2.88	2.51	1.90
Ni(II)—3-Cl <i>p</i> -CH ₃ G	3.58	3.19	2.28	1.59
Ni(II)—5-Cl <i>o</i> -CH ₃ G	3.42	2.94	2.44	1.84

* Values of formation constants in case of Cu(II) and Ni(II) chelates of glycine in aqueous medium were taken from the data used by Basolo and Chen⁶.

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